

1 Transcript

2 **Ida Manton**

3 06.06.2025

4 Transcribed with noScribe vers. 0.6.2

5 Edited by FN

6 **FN:** Let's start simple, with a short introduction. What is your role? And
7 in what capacity are you here?

8 **IM:** So, I have been teaching international negotiations, mediation,
9 conflict resolution, and various aspects and sub-disciplines from these
10 large fields in the last 20 years. I have been working for the OSCE as
11 full-time staff for more than seven years and as a consultant for some 20
12 years. And I come from a region that was really affected by conflicts, wars,
13 perpetual violence for many years.

14 These were very formative years of my life. So, while I started, as
15 somebody who wanted to study literature and art and, you know, the
16 beautiful aspects of humanity, I was very early in my life thrown in
17 conflicts, disagreements, misunderstandings, and really violent situations.
18 I realized that, the stories that were told were not the only outcome that
19 we could have had, that it could have been very different, and it could
20 have been much better. It really depended on the people who were making
21 decisions, people who were around the table.

22 Since the beginning of my career, I have been focusing on effective
23 communication, overcoming misunderstandings, and I'm here because
24 most of
25 the people who are here are colleagues that I work with in different
26 networks. They have been my mentors like Paul Meerts who was my
27 professor
28 at Leiden University, Valerie Rosaux and Raymond Saner who I have learned
29 a
30 lot from, then co-trainers and project partners like Frans Schram, but also
31 members in various networks we have created to cooperate and advance
32 the
33 field, like Francesco Marchi, , Remi Smolinski, , Dragos Vasilscu, Hrvoje
34 Zaric and many others. So, what I bring is a lot of experience from the
35 Western Balkans, but also a lot of research and work that I have done on
36 the history of the CSCE and OSCE, where I worked for many years, which I
37 thought for a long time was, you know, a sidekick to international
38 relations.

39 But I'm really offended now, that many people talk about Ukraine, Russia,
and the Balkans, and they really have no idea about the agreements that
were made from the 70s up until this day. There is so much ignorance and
so
much misunderstanding, and assumptions about why the things that are
happening now are happening without analysis. I think that we, the people

..4.3. Bridging Strateg

40 who have studied negotiations, who are teaching negotiations, have to have
41 more often meetings like this in order to understand it better, in order to
42 communicate and share different perspectives. Because we have spent our
43 lifetime looking at similar issues from different perspectives and those
44 need to find some congruence.

45 Those perspectives, need to be shared, because we learn from each other,
46 and I think that is the only way how we can make the world a better place.
47 Because I do still believe that even though I'm very cynical about what is
48 happening and very disappointed, but I still think that we know that it can
49 be better, because we have achieved better, and we know how to get there.

..4.1. Research / Practi

50 But unfortunately, the people who are dealing with resolving, mitigating,
51 and even mapping the actors and designing responses to the conflict, I
52 think, they're unprofessional, they're uninterested, and they're not the
53 people that we should, as people, as demos, give the legitimacy to those
54 people to decide for all of us. That we, as experts have a responsibility
55 to inform them and request from them to be more accountable, because
56 we're
57 talking about our lives, not just theirs.

57 **FN:** I'm very interested in this point, because we have quite some
58 submissions and quite some readers from regions that are currently in
59 conflict. What do you think was the central aspect that didn't pull you
60 into the violence you experienced around you, but rather say, that there's
61 something you need to do against that. I'm not going to be part of it. I'm
62 not going to be partisan in this idea.

63 **IM:** There were many calls, and even when I studied at Clingendael, I
64 remember at the end of my studies, one of my professors said: "so now
65 when
66 you go back, you will definitely go to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs."
67 And I said: "absolutely not!" Because I have been avoiding being part of
68 the political scene in my country and in the region for a long time, and
69 for good reasons. While we had really admirable leaders in the region, like
70 Zoran Đinđić in Serbia, for instance, and Budimir Lončar, the last foreign
71 minister of Yugoslavia, and thinkers, philosophers, rock stars even, who
72 shaped the culture, the social contract. There were so many writers. It was
73 such a vibrant community that war was not on the horizon anywhere. I think
74 that exact atmosphere and the conviction that we have social contract of
75 solidarity, anti-fascism, that we grew from the second world war, where we
76 knew on which side we are, that Yugoslavia was anti-fascist, non-aligned.
77 And that is a whole generation whose moral ethos was based on non-
78 aligned
79 human rights, universal rights.

..1.2. Social

78 I grew up in Libya because my mother was a doctor, building hospitals and
79 services for the people in Libya under Gaddafi. And the divisions that we
80 see today portray the world in a very black and white image. I don't like
81 that. I believe in diversity. And I think that, every liberal person who

..1.2. Social

82 calls themselves progressive, woke, intellectual is very hypocritical if
83 they're very liberal on one issue, but then very conservative on other
84 issues. And I think that we need social awakening of what that means.
When
85 you talk about freedoms and human rights, what does that mean? And how
can
86 you then project that to other people, other communities, have
87 understanding, have dialogue and work on that? Because it is not given.
88 It's not once and for all.

..1.2. Social

89 I think that these are concepts that we need to maintain, build, upgrade,
90 and convince ourselves that we're still on the right path because what
91 we're seeing now is very conservative, right-wing, fascist, openly fascist,
92 corrupt kleptocracies and captured state that don't mind supremacy and
93 feeling that they're better than other people. And I think we overcame that
94 in the Second World War, and this is why I never thought that I can be part
95 of the political system that, in different shapes and forms, finds ways to
96 put on the surface exactly these people, rather than those people who are
97 able to build bridges to bring dialogue as a platform for living, existing,
98 and sharing. And I think it's still there.
99 There is an author that I recently discovered, a historian, Rutger Bergman,
100 Dutch, who talks about moral ambition. And I think these are the kind of
101 events where we need to look for that moral ambition to be better as
102 individuals, to be better in smaller groups of intellectuals who are
103 committed towards that kind of change. But also, as a larger community
and
104 humanity, and to pull in those rogue elements who are spreading violence,
105 destruction, wars, bloodshed, towards our center, rather than to succumb
to

..4.2. Civil Society & N

106 their destructive narratives. That's why I never joined politics, and this
107 is why I believe that we need to be activists, researchers, and
108 intellectuals, and find platforms for sharing and being better people.

109 **FN:** Having this experience of the Yugoslavian environment you described,
110 this anti-fascist, art-centric, non-aligned environment that shifted
111 afterwards towards violence, and now experienced a quite enduring peace
112 process. Looking at the European Union, that is experiencing these kinds of
113 shifts that have the potential for violence and the strong political shifts
114 that we're experiencing from migration to climate. How do you see the way
115 we negotiate and we talk about these topics? What is the path we are going
116 down currently?

..2.1. European

117 **IM:** First of all, I think there are so many people, like myself, and many
118 of my friends from conflict regions, who have experienced dissolution of
119 their empire. Who have seen division within their communities, creation of
120 new administrative borderlines, and that can inform the European Union.
121 Actually, I'm just thinking of a project that I was invited by one of my
122 idols, John Packer, who is a human rights professor in Ottawa, a few years
123 ago. It was a project organized by Conciliation Resorce in UK. And the

124 project was on informing Georgia, informing the European Union regarding
125 Georgia from the experiences in Cyprus, Macedonia and Moldova. And I
think
126 these are valuable. And I think these are exactly the situations and
127 projects that can help Europe learn from the experiences in troubled
128 regions.

129 Because let me state something important. Yugoslavia was very peaceful
for
130 50 years after the war. Anti-fascist. Had very interesting structure. We
131 had a rotating presidency. It was a communist country. There were not
many
132 political options. That was the option. But it was a social contract where
133 social issues were taken care of. My education was for free. Healthcare was
134 for free. Yes, there was Goli otok. There were political prisoners. But we
135 know that there are many of those in the developed world as well. And I'm
136 not saying it was ideal. But when I lived in the Netherlands, I was talking
137 to one of my professors. And I said, that was a system that worked. There
138 was a dialogue. There were problems. They had parliament. They had
federal

139 government. And the problems were somehow negotiated. Why do you
think that

140 Europe is resistant to the same problems that destroyed Yugoslavia?

141 And how can we learn from that in order to make sure that the European
142 project doesn't fail? Because Yugoslavia was an equally enthusiastic
143 project. And, in fact, it actually worked for a very long time. And
144 Yugoslavia was mediator and well-respected in not only the non-aligned
145 world, but wherever I travel, people don't know what Macedonia is
nowadays.

146 But when I say former Yugoslavia and everywhere, people are like: "oh, I
147 know what that means." And they have high respect. So, without idealizing
148 what Yugoslavia was, I think what is important is to inform the European
149 Union from this kind of projects or temporary constructions that we've had,
150 that, first of all, alliances are not once and for all. And Europe knows
151 this very, very well.

152 Second of all, that institutionalizing some things that are about the soul
153 of Europe are making that very bureaucratic, technocratic. And by doing
154 that, we often lose the soul and the purpose of why we exist. And I think
155 it is very important to figure out how to learn from those experiences. And
156 there are ways, there are platforms. And I think that what is important for
157 Europe now is to make sure that we stay - and I say "we" because I live in
158 the Czech Republic - that we stay on course, that we remember what the
159 principles are, what the European project is, to continue reading
160 philosophy and be inspired by philosophers like Jan Patočka, Heidegger, in
161 time when we have a young population that likes instant gratification on

162 Twitter, and that's enough, right? We need to go back to basics, we need to
163 expand, have dialogue, and remember why Europe is so important. And if

..2.1. European

164
165
166
167

we
lose Europe, because Brexit was already a very, very serious sign that it might happen, like it happened to the Soviet Union, like it happened to Yugoslavia, like it happened to Czechoslovakia, right? The question is, if these changes happen without violence, that's a huge success, right? How to

168
169
170
171
172

avoid that? And we, I have a feeling that in the European Union, in the OSCE, in NATO, have not invested enough in preventing violent conflicts, and we can do much better there, as well as build capacities for mediation when the conflict arises, so it doesn't become entrenched, frozen, and perpetual.

173
174
175
176
177
178
179
180

FN: This is something I thought about a lot when I analyzed secessionist movements or any kind of conflicts that we really had in Europe. I really had the feeling, when I talked to people about my research, that Balkans is something people don't really have in the back of their mind. They know something happened there, they see the violence and the old pictures. Do you think the lessons that the Balkans actually learned over the time, and the tensions that are still there, and flaming up from time to time, is that enough reflected upon in the European Union?

181
182
183

IM: Absolutely not. And sadly, I think the European Union, in particular, is making huge mistakes, because they're uninformed about the past, that causes the current grievances, not only among politicians, but among people.

..2.1. European

184
185
186
187
188
189
190
191
192
193

Europe is making really bad and irreparable mistakes for instance in Macedonia, where I come from, that has been trying to start European negotiations for 25 years. And in the meantime, the neighbours that became members of the European Union are using fascist narratives for postponing that process. You would be thinking that these are European members who should make sure that all of the neighbourhood gets in, respects the same values, so that we can together fight anti-corruption, so we can together fight violation of human rights. But instead, we're seeing 19th century thinking and reviving of very ugly ghosts that are becoming the mainstream politics.

..2.1. European

194
195
196

And this is why people do not want to engage in politics, because we have been creating the supranational system to defend the citizens from their unwilling, unable governments when they are not providing what they should

197
198

be for their population. And if that system is a dormant dinosaur, then the people feel betrayed, and the people will then be either not involved, and we don't want democracy without public participation. That's exactly what

..4.2. Civil Society & N

199
200
201
202
203
204

we have in the Balkans, because when people are on the streets, like in Serbia, for months and months, if they don't get the support from above, Vucic will just remain in power. And then what is the point of civil activism? What is the point of active civil society? Why were we working for many years of having active civil society when the time comes, they're

..4.2. Civil Society & N 205

on their own?

206
207
208

FN: There seems to be a gap between what we know, what we do, and what civil society actually intends to do and organizes around. How do you think we can bridge these gaps?

..4.2. Civil Society & N 209

210
211
212

IM: Well, first of all, let me say something important. I think our civil society is not the civil society we had in the 70s, 80s, when we had dissident movements that were based on international law, like when Helsinki Final Act 50 years ago was adopted. It was a foundation for dissident movements in Czechoslovakia at the time, the Charter 77, and Václav Havel, and the whole group of people who were founding their worldview on international law. Solidarność, then you had dissidents in all of Central Europe that brought about the change in Europe, and that is fascinating. Now we don't have that anymore, because the people in Georgia

..4.2. Civil Society & N 218

219
220

go out on the street and say, we want to be free, we want different Georgia, but they're oppressed, they're attacked by their own government, and nobody's coming to the rescue. And the people in Serbia are facing the same

221
222
223
224
225

situation. And these are not political activists, precisely because if they are political activists, then they will be targets of the authoritarian regimes where they are. And they're saying, we are the students, we are the demos, we are the constituents, you're responsible to provide us with better services and better governance.

226
227
228
229
230
231
232
233
234

This is why we were building supranational guardians of the galaxy for a long time. And they're failing even to reprimand, to scold. They're failing to have dialogue with these autocrats. I'm not talking about regime change, but there's got to be something better that we can do when the call comes from the people, because it is the people, and it is about the people. And that change, really, if we don't see good examples, then what's the point of the whole universal human rights? This is how the whole system is, it is crumbling, and it is very difficult to then convince constituencies to get politically engaged.

235
236
237
238

FN: This sounds like the opposite of the common idea that the research and the politics will one day influence the civil society, while your idea is much more of a civil society that shows the needs that they have, and then they need the support of these structures.

..4.2. Civil Society & N 239

240
241
242

IM: Research and politics can influence civil society, but only after it takes off as a grassroots initiative. As such it can be informed by individuals who act locally and are often thinkers or knowledgeable activists who have passion for the cause they feel they can mobilize others around because solidarity and unity brings people together and then out on protests when dialogue is not possible. But also, let me just say something. The bad guys figured this out, okay? They know where to hit and where to

..4.2. Civil Society & N 244
245

..4.2. Civil Society & N

246
247
248
249
250
251
252
253
254
255
256
257
258
259
260

hurt. It's not a coincidence that the Trump administration attacks USAID first, because I see our time as a clash between the old rivalries of supremacy versus solidarity and humanity. So, the people who want to grab more for themselves, the people who believe they're better, the people who believe that they're first, and others are second and third, versus the people who believe in Human Rights Watch, Amnesty International, and humanitarian work we do all over the world. These are the two big camps that are fighting for which worldview will win. And this is why the battle in America was very important at the last elections. And it almost feels as if, you know, the supremacists and the right-wingers won, which gave a lot of strength to similar movements around the globe. But as I said, we, and it was said at the conference, we cannot see any events as a final destination. You know, these are just temporary things. You go one step further and maybe two steps back and so on and so on. That is why it is important to understand that this dialogue is necessary.

..4.2. Civil Society & N

261
262
263
264
265
266
267
268
269
270
271
272
273
274
275

In the meantime, the civil society organizations learn how to play the game that donors also need. They need to check a box and they need to have this many CSOs and we're working with these people, we're not working with these people. How much money have you used before? All of that became too bureaucratized and the people who have the soul but don't know how to play the game. They are out of the game. So, the usual suspects became, instead of NGOs, governmental, part of government. They're not non-governmental because many of them are doing this planning, structuring and so on with government. And that is done not only by China. It is done by the West as well. They have their usual friends, they're doing their projects, they trust each other, but that is not empowering real civil society that feels the real needs from the field, from the constituency. We need to get back to that dialogue. We need to have parliamentarians who know how to talk to their constituency, not only sitting in nice cars and nice offices in their buildings, but actually work on that dialogue.

..6.2. Anticipated Chal

..1.2. Social

276
277
278
279
280
281
282
283
284
285
286
287

So, I think that the links are broken between the people and their representatives. I think that we need to reestablish that. And once people trust that they give their legitimacy to somebody who represents them really and cares about carrying their message to the higher level where decisions are taken, then we can talk about democracy again. At the moment, we're lost in procedures. And we think we have democracies, but in fact, I, as a citizen, I don't feel very much that I'm participating in the society. Other people are, like: "don't worry, we have things under control." I'm, like: "no, but I don't want you to have things under control." I need you to talk to me in order to get my opinions higher up, right? And that is democracy. And that is what I think we got a little bit carried away and lost that momentum because we have lobbyists doing this work. We have paid

..2.1. European

..2.1. European

288

NGOs who think they are representing the people just because they have one

289

survey or two. So, I think that we need to get back to having real dialogue from, teenagers to inform us what their problems are, unions to inform us what their problems are. And these negotiations within society need to be informed by people that we saw here as well. You know, these are not just organizational glitches. These are real processes that improve our societies or take them into polarized communities and then for some of them

295

now it's too late.

296

FN: Looking at the communication and the broken links, what do you think are the skills that are needed to amend this?

297

298

IM: At different level there are different skills that are needed, right?

299

But I would argue that we underuse the potential that we have in our society. Recently I visited a doctor for some private issue and she said,

300

you're teaching international negotiations. I need that very often. And I

301

said, why? And she said, because various people come here and they tell

302

me

..4.3. Bridging Strategy

303

what they think I should do because they know themselves better. And I work

304

at the emergency ward and I know what I need to do and some of them are

305

violent, others are drunk, a third are coming with spouses and everybody

306

thinks that they know better. But I know and I'm the expert, I'm the doctor,

307

I need to just do my job. And I have a feeling that we as experts in

308

negotiation and mediation are not used as much as we should be used.

309

So, for instance, now in Ukraine, you have people who are politicians who

310

are negotiating because they read "The Art of the Deal" or because they did

..4.3. Bridging Strategy

311

some business negotiations. But we are lacking the expertise, we are

312

lacking the people who have been studying, writing books, saw the conflict

313

in Sudan, in the Balkans, they have been writing recommendations. We're

314

those brains. We're looking at Ukraine and we don't have even European task

315

force of the best and brightest who have the idea, who know the history,

316

who have studied all the Russian-Ukrainian conflicts, who know

317

constitutional law, who have read all the recommendations by the High

318

Commission on National Minorities, who know minority rights, who know the

319

the

319

CSCE, where are these people, why are they not sitting in one office

320

talking and thinking about how to save Ukraine non-stop? That's a job.

321

That's not a voluntary thing that all of us do a little bit of. I write a

322

book; you write a chapter. We need to sit together because this is crucial

323

for Europe and this is crucial for the world and if we are to save the

324

world that we created here in Paris in 1990 with the Charter of Paris for

325

New Europe. It's not ideal what was planned at that time. We need to

..6.2. Anticipated Chal

..6.2. Anticipated Chal

326 upgrade it and we need to maintain it and if we are to do that, we need to
327 have few buildings like this where people like us will be sitting with
328 politicians, with experts on former Soviet space and talk to each other and
329 to give that kind of body legitimacy to inform the political process, not
330 just to have think tanks here and there writing. "Maybe I read that report,
331 maybe not" but have this dialogue non-stop and open and inform each
other,

..2.1. European

332 learn from each other, and contribute because this is really important.
333 That's why my contribution at the conference was a little bit about the
334 history of the CSCE and what can we learn from this kind of processes
335 because I have a feeling everybody's talking about Ukraine, but most of the
336 people don't even know the history of the rapprochement between the East
337 and West, the dissolution of the Soviet Union and the anger felt by Russia
338 about the expansion, the anger felt by Ukrainians for not being able to
339 decide on their own what they want, the anger felt by all of us for the
340 Russian invasion and destruction of our system based on rules,
341 international law, human rights, universal human rights that obviously are
342 not applicable everywhere, and I think in general everybody's angry but the
343 dialogue is still missing.

344 **FN:** Do you think we have the skills and the capacity and the people who
345 would be able to do that but we're just not organizing them?

346 **IM:** Absolutely, and I also think that we know how to do these things, we
347 have done that before, we have reached from Helsinki, from Second World
War

348 to Helsinki, to Paris where we said the war is over, it was in the document
349 I mentioned at the conference called Joint Declaration of 22 States where
350 they said the parties to the war, to the Second World War, are signing that
351 the war is over, basta. We got there, it takes a long time, but what I'm
352 thinking is how can we use the knowledge from that period and do a
353 shortcut? And apply it. How can we do this faster? Time is an important
354 element in negotiations, but maybe if we identify what are the things that
355 have to be discussed, at what stage, what kind of segments, how do we
356 deepen the discussions, how do we reframe, redefine, find different
wording

..6.1. Research Que:

..5.1. Essential Skill:

357 that the Russians are not allergic to, that the Ukrainians can accept. I
358 think all of these are topics for experts and I'm looking forward to hear
359 from international experts who will advise the politicians how to overcome
360 these problems because I don't think that politicians are untrained or not
361 educated in the field of political science, philosophy, international
362 relations, they don't have the capacity to do it on their own just because
363 they're given the mandate from the people.

..4.1. Research / Practi

364 You need knowledge, you need experts, and I think that that needs to
happen
365 sooner rather than later. And before waiting to be invited, I think all of
366 us need to think about what their contribution to this would be. And that's
367 why I wrote a book with an American negotiator, John Maresca, who was

part
368 of that whole process of the detente between the East and West. And the
369 book is called Ukraine, Putin's War for the "Near Abroad". And we explain
370 what is at stake, what was violated with Russia's blatant and very rude,
371 very brutal invasion. And I think, I hope that people read our contribution
372 and that they can learn from experienced diplomat who is still alive and we
373 can collect more and more recollections from these people who created the
374 structure of security and cooperation in Europe. And I think we know how to
375 do that. we just need to go back to basics and figure out how to do a
376 shortcut before we enlarge the conflict and the scope of the conflict
377 because every day matters.

378 **FN:** Mentioning your book, if you think about a piece of media, a song,
379 theater, book, movie, that pertains to this negotiation, to how we can
380 interact with each other on this kind of level, what would you recommend?

381 **IM:** All of it. And non-stop. The more art, the more beautiful, aesthetized
382 interaction, the better. I cannot recommend one thing because I am female
383 dressed in flowers and pink and you don't look like me, you don't like the
384 same things like me. I have a daughter who plays rock guitar and she reads
385 different things, she watches different things. we all have different
386 sensors for inputs from the outside world and we need to be everywhere
and
387 as we heard John Lennon's Imagine, I want us to imagine different reality,
388 a better world together. I don't care where it comes from. Just make people
389 think about their moral ambition and do this sooner rather than later.

390 **FN:** Perfect. Thank you so much. That's such a nice ending. I love it. Thank
391 you very much.

392 **IM:** Thank you.